

RitrainPlus

Deliverable 2.3.
Report on the full set of
standardized Learning Activities-
M24

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Document History

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V1.0	22 Mar 2023	Draft version
V1.1	31 Mar 2023	Draft version submitted for team revision
V1.2	6 Apr 2023	Submission to Coordinator

Executive Summary

In this document we provide the design of Learning Activities developed in the framework of the **Task 2.2 - Engagement of Universities and design of the Learning Activities and Longitudinal Learning Tracks on managerial skills related to RIs and CFs** (led by UNIBO). LAs have been selected (at least 2 for each level of the European Qualification Framework 6, 7 and 8) and all organizational aspects were defined. The selection of the relevant activities was based on the results obtained from **Task 2.1 - Defining training needs and updating the competency profile** (co-led by CESSDA-Itp AUSSDA and CTLS) completed, as planned, during the first year, the results of which are reported in Deliverable [D2.1](#), publicly available in Zenodo.

This Deliverable contains, for each LA, a set of information that constitute a minimal set of feasible Teacher's kit to enable replication of the courses in any Universities, but should be considered a living document because an update of the Teacher's kits will be provided after the piloting of the courses in AY 23-24.

This work package, in overall terms, aims to develop training schemes and policies for the acquisition of the necessary transversal skills needed by operators and managers of RIs and CFs with the joint effort of Research Infrastructures (RI), Core Facilities (CF) and Universities, so that multiple beneficiaries or third parties cooperate in the realization of each Teacher's kit and are involved in piloting the courses.

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Introduction

A set of new Learning Activities (LAs) is offered to students belonging to different university programmes, at different EQF levels, enabling them to develop a specific career path to become the future operators and managers of RIs and CFs. The management of research services, requires a broad spectrum of soft skills and a business-like approach to running an organization as a service to a community. These RIs require knowledge and competence to deal with issues such as multinational operations, transnational access and data flow, different Legal, Ethical and Social Issues.

The LAs on each topic are prepared at the three EQF levels and will be offered in the next AY building a longitudinal learning track (LLT) throughout the whole academic career but can be acquired also all together at EQF8.

From a **methodological point of view**, the development of the LAs adopted the following criteria:

1. **Needs** expressed by the RIs/CFs and the **prospective elaboration** of these needs with respect to the training of university students;
2. **Tuning of topics and methods** for the LAs with respect to the different EQF levels;
3. **Replicability, scalability** of the LAs and their alignment with the **European guidelines** on micro-credentials.

As regards point 1., the definition of the topics considered the needs expressed by the RIs/CFs as (1) emerged in Task 2.1 and described in Deliverable 2.1. "Identifying and Updating Training Needs in European Research Infrastructures and Core Facilities", (2) recognized in more localized training experiences such as the Executive Masters in Management of Research Infrastructures at the University of Milan Bicocca¹. These needs have been elaborated in perspective in order to project the enhancement of the skills acquired from the outset in university training for future researchers/users of the RIs/CFs and future operators and managers of these RIs/CFs. In this sense, priority has been given to soft and transversal skills. It should be noted that, to the best of our knowledge, there is no integrated and comprehensive experience in Europe of training courses already started in universities.

As regards point 2., the choice of topics favored a broader and more introductory scope for EQF6, intermediate for EQF7, and more specific for EQF8. Therefore, the training path for the first levels seems more groundbreaking (compared to the curricular activities currently envisaged in Europe for these levels), while for the EQF8 level the LAs proposed are basically in line with the more advanced but already known transversal skills proposed for PhD students.

As regards point 3., the design of the LAs was coherent with, and inspired by, the European guidelines on micro-credentials². Flexibility and scalability have been particularly considered. In particular, LAs have been developed to be potentially and modularly recombinable in the three EQF levels are proposed. Moreover, precisely to allow the experimentation of different models in a field hitherto unexplored from an institutional point of view, the LAs have a different granularity of articulation and different internal formats, a differentiation also necessary in the light of the diverse themes.

¹ <https://emmri.unimib.it>

² <https://education.ec.europa.eu/education-levels/higher-education/micro-credentials>

Selected LAs

The results of the D2.1 have been deeply discussed by the team and summarized into two main fields of competencies required to future managers of RIs and CFs: Interpersonal communication and the knowledge of the RI and CF word.

“The world of RIs and CFs” field focused on the academic excellence and understanding of the field of research, the importance of project management, especially regarding leadership and people-managing skills, the necessity of a political and strategical development, considering the funding schemes and opportunity of cooperation raising in Europe. Finally, the need for a flexible approach along with a fundamental basic knowledge of data management, open science ethical legal and social implications.

The communication field referred to the need of providing students with a knowledge of: the variety of stakeholders of the research field, the importance of developing managerial skills, of understanding the structures and the communication needs of the scientific community. A special focus was reserved to learning the importance of cooperation between different disciplines as much as considering science and society as whole and finally learning the importance and balance of working with others.

Starting from the definition of these two areas of competence, the participants to Task 2.2 selected a subset of learning activities (LAs), at least two for each EQF level (Bachelor, Master and PhD):

The Task2.2 participants were then divided into groups, each composed by one leader and two collaborators, in order to contribute to the design of the learning activities in accordance with their fields of expertise and experience.

To facilitate the collection of information a [sheet](#) that will consist of the bases of the Teacher’s kit of each LAs together with the [course description](#) was prepared and collected as follow.

The Teacher’s kits are very flexible and can be utilized for students of different background and EQF level. LAs may be adapted to higher/lower EQF levels by deepening/reducing the technical aspects of specific presented methodology. In addition, selected cases studies may be added if the Unit are targeted to students in specific fields.

In addition, if the LAs are adapted to students having a low level of specialization, and awareness of both scientific and technological aspects, it is suggested to shift from intensive courses format (2-3 days) to longer format (2-3 weeks).

The LAs can be scaled to match also the demands of both early career-researchers and PIs of projects, who want to get insight into those topics. However, there are logistical limitations on how many learners can participate and get adequate feedback (max. of 30 in the current setup)

The European RI/CF in ERA: An Introduction

LEVEL EQF6 ■ EQF7 EQF8

ECTS	3
LA Aims	The course aims at introducing the students to the topic of RIs/CFs, both from the conceptual side and from the practical (i.e., managerial) perspective. After an introductory unit on the concept and general issues of RI/CF and on the socio-economic impact of RIs/CFs, three specific parts of the course will address specificities and management problems for three areas of research: Social Sciences and Humanities, Physical Sciences and Engineering and Life Sciences. In each part, the theoretical content is illustrated through references to existing RI/CF and cases studies.
Learning Goals	<p>Upon completion of this LA students will have demonstrated a basic knowledge of what a research infrastructure (RI) and a core facility (CF) are. In particular, they are expected to have learnt:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the elements of common definitions of RIs/CFs; (b) how RIs/CFs support methods and scientific communities; (c) the difficulties and challenges behind different types of RIs. (d) the taxonomy of socio-economic benefits and costs associated to RI/CF, and real-world examples of applications of such taxonomy (e) the CBA model as applied to RIs/CFs (f) the measurement issues associated to various types of benefits and costs; (g) the definition and use of the NPV test for evaluation of the socio-economic impact of RIs/CFs.
Specific Learning Outcomes (LOs):	<p>The following are the main LOs expected for this course:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The learner is able to explain the fundamentals of the concept of RI/CF; ● The learner can explain in detail the Pros & Cons of the different types of RI: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. Distributed research infrastructure II. Single-sited research infrastructure III. Virtual infrastructure. ● The student has a basic knowledge of what is meant for socio-economic impact of RI/CF. In particular, they are able <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. to list and discuss the various types of benefits and costs associated to RIs/CFs; II. to classify benefits and costs associated to specific RIs/CFs using the proposed taxonomy III. to identify some difficulties and challenges in the measurement of benefits and costs associates to RIs./CFs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Given a specific proposal, the learner can describe the steps to get on the ESFRI Roadmap process ● In regard to the three ERC sectors, the learner is able to define, at a general level, the difference in relation to the following aspects: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. The goal and type of RI II. The approach used to collect FAIR data III. The specific Methods and Tools utilized IV. The Networks in which the RI is included V. The Impact of Research VI. The Society engagement
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Main characteristics of the course

Format	Synchronous Online Course Delivery
Pedagogical methods/tools:	Lectures and group practicals
Assessment methods:	Formative assessment - making use of the actual work that students produce in the classroom and/or practical test such as challenges; online tests Summative assessment – Online test with close questions
Evaluation:	Preparation on a number of topics covered in the course, ability to make independent choices of critical analysis, mastery of specific terminology. with questions, all answers have to be correct
LA Leader	UniBo
LA Participants	UniParis1, UMIL

Course Description

The course does not require any specific knowledge background.

The course is organized in 5 teaching units consisting in lectures and group practicals with case study:

UNIT	TITLE	TEACHER
1	Introduction to RI/CF	Antonino Rotolo - UniBo
2	The socio-economic impacts of RI/CF	Lorenzo Zirulia - UMIL
3	RI/CF for Social Sciences and Humanities	Silvye Jolly – UniParis1

4	RI/CF for Physical Sciences and Engineering	Daniele Bonaccorsi - UniBo
5	RI/CF for Life Sciences	Gerardo D'Errico -UMIL

Unit 1: Introduction to RI/CF

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
What are a Research Infrastructure and a Core Facility? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe what a Research Infrastructure is. Be aware of different perspectives on the definition of research infrastructures 	Lecture: Antonino Rotolo - UniBo	25 min
Interoperability <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe what is data for research purposes, and identify your own data Describe Standards, explain their importance and how researchers make use of them. 	Lecture: Antonino Rotolo - UniBo	25 min
Breakout Rooms - Students are invited to discuss the following topic: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How do you see future RI/CF in your university discipline? Can you give examples of how RI/CF are important in your curriculum? 	Breakout rooms: students in smaller sub-rooms or sub-groups and feedback from a rapporteur	30 min
Methods and Tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understand the kinds of methods research infrastructures can facilitate Be aware of the kinds of tools offered by research infrastructures, where to find them, and the benefits they can bring to research 	Lecture: Antonino Rotolo - UniBo	25 min
Networks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Know what networks exist within the research infrastructure ecosystems 	Lecture: Antonino Rotolo - UniBo	25 min
Breakout Rooms - Students are invited to discuss the following topic: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What tools do you expect from RI/CF based on your university experience? 	Breakout rooms: students in smaller sub-rooms or sub-groups and feedback from a rapporteur	30 min
Research Impact	Lecture: Antonino Rotolo - UniBo	25 min

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Give a definition of impact and know how it can be measured for an individual researcher • Understand the mutual beneficial relationship between researchers and research infrastructures 		
<p>Critiques and Issues</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be aware of some of the debates and critiques surrounding research infrastructure 	Lecture: Antonino Rotolo - UniBo	25 min
<p>Breakout Rooms - Students are invited to discuss the following topic:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How do you see research in 30 years based on what we have learned so far? 	Breakout rooms: students in smaller sub-rooms or sub-groups and feedback from a rapporteur	30 min

Teaching Materials

5 minutes video pills presenting RI and CF, all the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website

https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1ZJL0YCFR_GQFsrD-IGAbE-G505BzDAZ- (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

<http://training.parthenos-project.eu/sample-page/intro-to-ri/>

<https://campus.dariah.eu/curriculum/the-parthenos-complete-guide-to-research-infrastructures>

Unit 2: The socio-economic impacts of RI/CF

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
The first part aims to introduce students with the topic of socio-economic impact of RI/CF, with a focus on the <i>conceptual</i> foundations.	the theoretical content is illustrated through references to existing RI/CF and cases studies of socio-economic impact analysis	2 hours
The socio-economic impacts of RI/CF: introductory notes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The cost and benefits of science</i> • <i>Paradigms: little science, big science, RI/CF</i> 	Lecture: Lorenzo Zirulia - UMIL	30 min
The socio-economic impact of RI/CF: the cost benefit analysis view <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>A taxonomy of socio-economic benefits and costs associated to RI/CF</i> • <i>Illustrating the taxonomy through examples of RI/CF</i> • <i>Preliminary conclusions</i> 	Lecture: Lorenzo Zirulia - UMIL	90 min
The second part aims to provide a more detailed account of the cost-benefit <i>model</i> as applied to RI/CF, with a focus of the measurement issues of socio-economic benefits and costs.	the theoretical content is illustrated through references to existing RI/CF and cases studies of socio-economic impact analysis	2 hours
The socio-economic impact of RI/CF: the cost benefit analysis (CBA) model <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The CBA model for RI/CF: definition</i> • <i>The basic ingredients: use benefits, non-use benefits and costs</i> 	Lecture: Lorenzo Zirulia - UMIL	30 min
The cost benefit analysis (CBA) model for RI/CF: the cost side <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The cost side: measurement issues</i> • <i>The LHC case</i> 	Lecture: Lorenzo Zirulia - UMIL	15 min
The cost benefit analysis (CBA) model for RI/CF: the benefit side <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The benefit side: scientific publications</i> • <i>The benefit side: human capital</i> 	Lecture: Lorenzo Zirulia - UMIL	60 min

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The benefit side: technological impact on firms</i> • <i>The benefit side: production of good and services</i> • <i>The benefit side: RI/CF as cultural goods</i> 		
<p>Introducing the Net Present Value (NPV) test</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The NPV test: definition</i> • <i>The NPV test: use and interpretation</i> 	Lecture: Lorenzo Zirulia - UMIL	15 min

The present Unit has been built from a module of the course “European Research and Innovation Policies” (Prof. Massimo Florio; UMIL), offered at the EQF7 level.

In line with the target audience (EQF6), the emphasis is NOT on the purely technical aspects of cost-benefit analysis but more on the conceptual dimension of benefits and costs of RIs.

Teaching Materials

All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1ZJL0YCfR_GQFsrD-IGAbE-G505BzDAZ- (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

Florio, M. (2019). *Investing in science: Social cost-benefit analysis of research infrastructures*. Mit Press (Introduction and Chapter 1). Interested students may be referred to the other chapter of Florio’s book for more detailed discussion of the content of this Unit, including the references to original sources of cases studies/examples.

Unit 3: RI/CF for SSH

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
The first part aims to introduce students with the topic of RI/CF for SSH in the conceptual side. The second part includes three case studies to familiarize students with the concepts seen previously through practical perspectives from guest speakers.		2 hours
Introduction to SSH <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Characteristics of Social Sciences, and Humanities</i> • <i>Description of the list of disciplines adapted from the UNESCO International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED 2011)</i> 	Lecture: Sylvie JOLLY (UniParis1) Video watching	30 min
Research in SSH <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Values and societal challenges</i> • <i>Data Openness and FAIRness</i> • <i>RI/CF for SSH: types and usefulness</i> 	Lecture: Sylvie JOLLY (UniParis1) Video watching	30 min
SSH RI and the EU strategy <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Definition of ERA</i> • <i>ESFRI SCI WG, Roadmap, Projects and Landmarks</i> 	Lecture: Sylvie JOLLY (UniParis1) Video watching	60 min
The second part includes three case studies to familiarize students with the concepts seen previously through practical perspectives from guest speakers.		2 hours
Case Study 1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>OPERAS RI and the GoTriple platform</i> 	Case analysis and discussion by a Guest Speaker (TBC) <i>Suzanne Dumouchel</i> <i>Partnership coordinator of OPERAS RI</i> <i>Director of EOSC Association</i> <i>Head of European Cooperation at DDOR (CNRS)</i> https://cnrs.academia.edu/SuzanneDumouchel/CurriculumVitae	60 min

Case Study 2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>University of Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne RI/CF ecosystem</i> 	Case analysis and discussion by <i>Sylvie JOLLY</i>	30 min
Case study 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Una Europa/UNA.Resin: a R&I ecosystem on Cultural Heritage under construction</i> 	Case analysis and discussion by a Guest Speaker <i>Ekaterina Smoliakova</i> <i>Project Manager UNA.Resin</i>	30 min

Teaching Materials

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Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

- FAIR Data in Social Sciences and Humanities: a Triple Open Science Training Session

<https://roadtofair.hypotheses.org/327>

- ESFRI Glossary

<https://www.esfri.eu/glossary>

- ESFRI Roadmap

<https://www.esfri.eu/esfri-roadmap>

- ESFRI Roadmap 2021 | Landscape Analysis | Social & Cultural Innovation domain

<https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/landscape-analysis/section-1/social-cultural-innovation/>

- OPERAS RI

<https://operas-eu.org/>

- GOTriple Platform

<https://gotriple.eu/>

- An Animated Introduction to Social Science

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DSIdaTSG2Gg&t=237s>

- A Day in the Life of a Data Archivist

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7gvvQ5i7B34&list=PLSzjTR7L6XhGb8h3SMG3e8-HOdNq13PyW&index=10>

- Make Your Research Data F.A.I.R

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=klwHJ6DkFdc&list=PLSzjTR7L6XhGb8h3SMG3e8-HOdNq13PyW&index=12>

- RIs addressing challenges: Culture | 1st ESFRI Stakeholders Forum Meetup | 15.9.22 | Brussels

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ktvFCGd7J14>

- CESSDA Presentation

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1EyS4u-anVo>

- GoTriple promotional video October 2021

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4HCNt1nZ2I0>

- Discovery (TRIPLE Video Tutorial Series)

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PHv2NLYQQbs>

Unit 4: RI/CF for Physical Sciences and Engineering

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
<p>What are a Research Infrastructure and a Core Facility? Specific aspects in Physical Sciences and Engineering</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe what a Research Infrastructure is in Physical Sciences and Engineering. Be aware of different perspectives on the definition of research infrastructures in Physical Sciences and Engineering Gaps, Challenges and Future Needs 	Lecture: Daniele Bonaccorsi - UniBo	30 min
<p>Breakout Rooms - Students are invited to discuss the following topic:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What tools do you expect from the RI/CF discussed so far based on your university experience? 	Breakout rooms: students in smaller sub-rooms or sub-groups and feedback from a rapporteur	30 min
<p>Case Study 1</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Open Physics Hub at the Physics and Astronomy Department 	Lecture: Daniele Bonaccorsi - UniBo	30 min
<p>Breakout Rooms - Students are invited to discuss the following topic:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What experiment or scientific activity would you plan for Open Physics Hub? How do you design the governance of it? 	Breakout rooms: students in smaller sub-rooms or sub-groups and feedback from a rapporteur	30 min
<p>Case Study 2</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Research Centre in High-Performance Computing, Big Data and Quantum Computing, Bologna, Italy 	Lecture: Daniele Bonaccorsi - UniBo	30 min
<p>Breakout Rooms - Students are invited to discuss the following topic:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What experiment or scientific activity would you plan for Open Physics Hub? 	Breakout rooms: students in smaller sub-rooms or sub-groups and feedback from a rapporteur	30 min

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> How do you design the governance of it? 		
Case Study 3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> CERN, Geneva, Switzerland 	Lecture: Daniele Bonaccorsi - UniBo	30 min
Breakout Rooms - Students are invited to discuss the following topic: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What experiment or scientific activity would you plan for CERN? How do you design the governance of it? 	Breakout rooms: students in smaller sub-rooms or sub-groups and feedback from a rapporteur	30 min

Teaching Materials

All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1ZJL0YCfR_GQFsrD-IGAbE-G505BzDAZ- (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

<https://roadmap2021.esfri.eu/landscape-analysis/section-1/physical-sciences-engineering/>
<https://site.unibo.it/openphysicshub/en>
<https://www.supercomputing-icsc.it/en/icsc-home/>
<https://www.home.cern>

Unit 5: RI/CF for Life Sciences

The Unit aims at providing a historical overview focusing on the design, development and management of a core microscopy facility for users with different interests in Life Sciences and of how the facility's development process was led. How the work organisation and tasks of the lab manager and technical staff are carried out, and how the financial management of a core facility is run.

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
<p>How to build a bio-imaging facility.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The student know the reasons that led to the creation of a facility of this type which was raised mainly from the need of researchers involved in the study of "life sciences" to be able to access the use of state-of-the-art instruments, that would be difficult to be purchased by single labs.</i> • <i>The student will also acquire technical knowledge about the different types of instrumentation made available and will understand the reasons for the need to have different types of microscopes.</i> 	Lecture: Gerardo D'Errico (UMIL)	90 min
<p>Learn how to organise the work of the technicians and the management of the users.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The student will be educated about the different types of services offered and how to manage internal users (from the university field) with different technical and scientific backgrounds as well as in the case of private companies. It will be taught in which situations the service may concern an autonomous use of the devices compared to when instead it will be necessary to take advantage of technical support.</i> 	Lecture: Gerardo D'Errico (UMIL)	90 min
<p>Learn how to financially manage the facility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The student will learn the management model adopted for credit recovery, the purchase of new equipment as well as the need to allocate</i> 	Lecture: Gerardo D'Errico (UMIL)	60 min

<i>resources for its maintenance will be presented.</i>		
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Teaching Materials

The teaching does not have a dedicated book and all the material will be provided by teachers. All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1Z1L0YCFR_GQFsrD-IGAbE-G505BzDAZ- (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

Interdisciplinary work: make the team effective

LEVEL EQF6 EQF7 EQF8

ECTS	3
LA Aims	The LA is focused on providing the learners with the practical knowledge necessary to work efficiently in teams and to develop increasingly healthy interpersonal relationships. Dealing with differences successfully and without burnout.
Learning Goals	Upon completion of this LA students will have demonstrated a basic knowledge of how to work efficiently in teams. In particular, they are expected to have learnt: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> how to work with people of different profiles in a harmonious and efficient way; how to form, shape and maintain cohesive, empowered and cohesive teams focused on both people and results; how to manage nonconformities and conflicts in a positive and fruitful way; how to plan in a challenging and realistic way.
Specific Learning Outcomes (LOs):	The following are the main LOs expected for this course: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The learner is able to explain the fundamentals of the interpersonal communication process. The learner is able to list the main aspects that can influence the efficiency of a team.

Main characteristics of the LA

Format	MOOC and in presence activity
Pedagogical methods/tools:	Self study, lectures, group practicals and learning by doing
Assessment methods:	Embedded assessments (i.e., making use of the actual work that students produce in the classroom) and/or practical test (such as challenges).
Evaluation:	Participation in and use of the practical exercises during the course. The MOOC is considered properly completed if the participant responds correctly to 60 % of the questions in total . After completing the course, you can download and print a certificate of participation .

LA Leader	UCM
LA Participants	UniBo

Course Description

The course does not require any specific knowledge background. The course is organized in 2 teaching units consisting of a on line MOOC and in lectures and group practicals with case study:

UNIT	TITLE	TEACHER
1	On line MOOC Working in Multidisciplinary Teams	Self study
2	Working in team	Jan Luis Fuentes - UPM

Unit 1: Mooc course at UNIBO

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
The course, based on Bruce Tuckman’s model of group/team development, will show you the different difficulties and challenges that groups/teams need to face during the different stages of their development in order to become a High-Performing Team .	Self-study following the MOOC instructions	5 weeks

Teaching Materials

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

https://book.unibo.it/courses/course-v1:Unibo+WMT101+2023_E1/about

Unit 2: UCM

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
Interpersonal communication process <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The social brain. ● Intrapersonal and interpersonal intelligence ● The neural wifi: how it influences creating culture and the environment. How to use it to our advantage 	Lectures: Jan Luis Fuentes - UCM	4 h
Team characteristics and efficiency <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Characteristics and differences between a work group and a team. When is one necessary and when is the other. ● Stages in the formation of teams and characteristic situations that occur in them. ● Team alliance and values 	Lectures: Jan Luis Fuentes - UCM	4 h
The iE.E.H!! tool to be a good team player	Group work	4 h
Solving problems <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Focused ● Dysfunctions in a team and how to deal with them. ● Conflict resolution and negotiation. ● How trust can be restored if it is broken. 	Lectures: Jan Luis Fuentes - UCM	4h

Teaching Materials

Projector, slide show, loudspeakers; blank paper, posits, coloured pencils or markers, insulating tape

All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website

<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/13JSAvibrVVTxzYtGD3wMtgipcVjhO1Ej> (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

ELSI – Ethical legal and Societal Implication

LEVEL EQF6 EQF7 EQF8

ECTS	2
LA Aims	The course aims at creating knowledge of all the issues related to research in Core Facilities and Research Infrastructure, giving to Masters’ students an insight to the relevant stakeholders involved in research and the different ethical and legal issues such as: Research Integrity, Equity, Diversity and Inclusion, GDPR general Framework, Public Engagement and Citizen Science.
Learning Goals	Upon completion of this LA students will have demonstrated a basic knowledge of Ris’ and CFs’ role in the research field, gaining a first approach to the possible professional path. In particular, they are expected to have learnt the fundamental knowdlege about: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) Research Integrity (b) Equity, diversity and inclusion (c) GDPR and data in research (d) Public engagement and citizen science.
Specific Learning Outcomes (LOs)	<p>The following are the main LOs expected for this course:</p> <p>Research Integrity (Unit 1):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. fully define the concept of research integrity; II. list the main principles of research integrity and properly describe each of them; III. compare the correct and incorrect types of conduct in research infrastructures; IV. construct practical examples on the basis of the lessons learned. <p>Equity, Diversity and Inclusion (Unit 2):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. know the three concepts of Equity, Diversity and Inclusion and the non-discrimination principle; II. describe and list different elements of diversity; III. understand the importance of diversity in RI; IV. discuss how DE&I can be implemented in research infrastructures. <p>GDPR (Unit 3):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. know the history and evolution of privacy and GDPR II. recognize the field of application and the subjects involved

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> III. being able to list the different principles that regulate the GDPR IV. being able to distinguish the different categories of data V. identify and distinguish the responsibilities of the subjects involved VI. understanding how to design an efficient informed consent VII. knowing the “dark patterns” <p>Public Engagement and Citizen science (Unit 4):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> I. know what Public Engagement is, the stakeholders; II. compare current approaches and practices for Public engagement actions; III. analyse the impacts of public engagement; IV. discuss examples in different domains; V. describe the history and definition of citizen science; VI. compare types of citizen science activities within different domains; VII. discuss examples of citizen science projects; VIII. discuss how RIs can enable (or inadvertently hinder) citizen science through their operating principles and design.
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Main characteristics of the LA

Format	Online with synchronous learning and the possibility for professors to record their lessons and upload it on the faculty platform in order to allow students to rewatch it. Possibility to transform it in face-to-face course.
Pedagogical methods/tools:	Lectures, analysis of case studies, role plays
Assessment methods:	Individual assessment
Evaluation:	Multiple choice test
LA Leader	UniTrento
LA Participants	UniBo, UH,

Course Description

The course aims at introducing ethical, legal and societal implications of research with a focus and an introduction to RIs and CFs. The course can be organized in 3 weeks, 2 blocks of 2 hours per week, or as

intensive course of 2 days 6 hours/days. We expect to run n.4 teaching units consisting in lectures and group practicals:

UNIT	TITLE	TEACHER
1	Research Integrity	Lucia Busatta - UniTrento
2	Equity, Diversity and Inclusion	Lucia Busatta - UniTrento
3	GDPR General Framework	Francesco Di Tano - UniBO
4	Public Engagement and Citizen science	Marco Peura - UH

Unit 1: Research Integrity

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
Introduction and definition of research integrity (RI) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It will be given to the participants a complete definition of research integrity. 	Lecture – theoretical part: Lucia Busatta - UniTrento	10 min
The importance of research integrity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It will be discussed why research integrity is an important matter; there will also be an historical digression on how the concept of research integrity developed over time, where in the world it began to evolve and why (Tuskegee Syphilis Study case). 	Lecture – theoretical part: Lucia Busatta - UniTrento	20 min
Principles of research integrity in the research infrastructures <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Which are the principles of research integrity, what are the different research misconducts and how to deal with them. The principles under consideration are contained into the European Code of Conduct; it will be given 5' per each principle (20' for the 4 principles): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> honesty (5') reliability (5') respect (5') accountability (5') The research misconduct and violations will also be analyzed during this part of the lesson. While discussing each misconduct or incorrect behavior, the professor will also give some practical examples. It will be given 5' for each research misconduct: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> FFP (falsification, fabrication, plagiarism) (5') Conflict of interests (10') Other unacceptable practices (related to authorship) (5'). 	Lecture – theoretical part: Lucia Busatta - UniTrento	40 min
Where to apply the core values of research integrity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Who is a researcher, where the core values of research integrity should be applied: 	Lecture – theoretical part: Lucia Busatta - UniTrento	20 min

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • in researchers (by themselves, their moral values) • in the relationship with colleagues • in research infrastructures (eg: use of scientific equipment, respect for the institution). • into research itself. 		
<p>Introduction of the practical part and instruction of the game</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It will be proposed to the students a quiz game regarding a realistic dilemma related to professionalism and integrity in research. The students will be asked to confront with particular dilemmas based on the past theoretical lesson on research integrity. 	Group work – practical part	15 min
<p>Game time</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The class will be divided into groups and each group will perform in front of the class while explaining its point of view. Each group will also choose his or her speaker who is going to explain the group position in front of the class. 	Group work – practical part	40 min
<p>Game results and final greetings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • After coming back to the main room each group speaker will explain his/her group choice and decision. By that point the professor will show the correct answer and the reason behind it. 	Group work – practical part	35 min

Teaching Materials

Slides, videos, existing codes, publications, and examples of practical cases, rubrics for assessments. All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1v8ExhiSsgIgnon7fihlL0y4OadE-E6wW> (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

- ALLEA: The European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
<https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/>
- CNR Guidelines for Research Integrity
https://www.cnr.it/sites/default/files/public/media/doc_istituzionali/ethics/guidelines-for-research-integrity-2019.pdf Research integrity codes of conduct in Europe: Understanding the divergences
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/bioe.12851>
- ENERI: Codes, Guidelines and Recommendations
<https://eneri.eu/codes-of-conduct/>

- ENRIO: Recommendations for the Investigation of Research Misconduct

<https://eneri.eu/ri-handbook/>

- EC: European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructure

https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/partners-networking/access-research-infrastructure/access-european-research-infrastructures_en

- How to create a RIPP (Research Integrity Promotion Plan)

https://sops4ri.eu/wp-content/uploads/Implementation-Guideline_FINAL.pdf

- Seven Reasons to Care about Integrity in Research

<https://www.scienceeurope.org/our-resources/seven-reasons-to-care-about-integrity-in-research>

Unit 2: Diversity, Equity and Inclusion

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
<p>Introduction and definition of DE & I</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What is diversity, what is equity, what is inclusion: their definitions and differences. A definition of the principle of non-discrimination as a basis for DE&I.</i> • <i>There will be taken into account the different international and European legal sources (European Convention on Human Rights, Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, etc...) in order to understand how the law protects people from discrimination.</i> • <i>Brief references to national constitutions will also be made.</i> 	<p>Lecture and general discussion – theoretical part: Lucia Busatta - UniTrento</p>	<p>15 min</p>
<p>Elements of diversity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Different forms of diversity will be analyzed with proper definitions and examples: ethnicity, sexual orientation, socioeconomic status, gender identity, religion, language, age, marital status, mental ability, physical abilities and disabilities.</i> 	<p>Lecture and general discussion – theoretical part: Lucia Busatta - UniTrento</p>	<p>10 min</p>
<p>Why to improve DE & I in research infrastructures</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>It will be discussed why we need to improve DE&I in research and why we should embrace diversity.</i> 	<p>Lecture and general discussion – theoretical part: Lucia Busatta - UniTrento</p>	<p>10 min</p>
<p>How to foster DE&I in research</p> <p><i>It will be discussed how stereotypes and other forms of bias can overshadow the strategic benefits of diversity, taking into consideration three main different forms of incorrect behaviors which may affect a research environment:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Harassment</i> • <i>Bullying</i> • <i>Prejudice.</i> <p><i>It will be finally examined how to work on these situations considering three different points of view:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The victim</i> • <i>The witness</i> • <i>The aggressor.</i> 	<p>Lecture – video watching: Lucia Busatta - UniTrento</p>	<p>25 min</p>

<p><i>It will be finally proposed a short video on inclusive practices in research environment (e.g.: https://youtu.be/rS4ci68dGc4).</i></p>		
<p>Welcome, introduction of the practical part and</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>The professor will welcome the class and introduce this module</i> 	Group work – practical part	5 min
<p>Instructions for the first group activity “DE&I in flower petals”</p> <p><i>The goal of this activity are:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>to reflect on what defines one’s identity and how people define themselves in relation to others</i> <i>to share aspects of participants’ identity and look for commonalities and differences</i> <i>to grasp the complexity and variability of the concept of identity.</i> <p><i>The class will be divided into groups. Each group should get a large art paper and draw a giant flower with a round center and an equal number of petals to the number of participants in the group. After discussion, each participant should fill the petals with something unique about themselves- anything that makes them stand out from others. However, physical characteristics should be ignored. Every group should fill the center of the flower with their ‘common’ element.</i></p>	Group work – practical part	5 min
<p>Working group (in breakout rooms)</p> <p><i>The class will be split into different groups and carry out the activity.</i></p>	Group work – practical part	20 min
<p>General reporting</p> <p><i>The classroom will return to the main room and each group speaker will report about the flower: each team should share the flowers with the other groups to discuss the differences and similarities.</i></p>	General discussion – practical part	10 min
<p>Second activity “I am but I’m not” instructions</p> <p><i>The professor will introduce the “I am but I’m not” game and give instructions about this second activity. The</i></p>	Personal work play – practical part	5 min

<p><i>goal of this activity is to dispel stereotypes and involve everyone in fostering a more inclusive culture. This activity will be taken in single players: each participant should take a piece of paper and make two columns with headers “I am...” and “I am not...” with the word “But” in between. E.g.: “I am a woman, but I am not weak.”</i></p>		
<p>Game play “I am but I’m not <i>Each participant will be given 5 min. to create its own quote.</i></p>	<p>Personal work play – practical part</p>	<p>5 min</p>
<p>Reading of the quotes and final greetings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Each participant will read its quote in front of the class.</i> 	<p>General discussion – practical part</p>	<p>10 min</p>

Teaching Materials

<https://blog.vantagecircle.com/activities-diversity-and-inclusion/>
<https://www.hivelearning.com/site/resource/diversity-inclusion/defy-stereotypes-i-am-but-i-am-not/>

All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1v8ExhiSsgIgnon7fihlL0y4OadE-E6wW> (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

- Research Integrity and Peer Review: Improving equity, diversity, and inclusion in academia
<https://researchintegrityjournal.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s41073-022-00123-z>
- Hacking Diversity with Inclusive Decision Making
https://www.cloverpop.com/hubfs/Whitepapers/Cloverpop_Hacking_Diversity_Inclusive_Decision_Making_White_Paper.pdf
- EC: She Figures, Gender in Research and Innovation
<https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/knowledge-publications-tools-and-data/interactive-reports/she-figures-2021>
- EC: Gender equality in Research and Innovation
https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en
- The European Charter for Researchers
https://euraxess.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/am509774cee_en_e4.pdf
- EC: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025
https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/policies/justice-and-fundamental-rights/gender-equality/gender-equality-strategy_en
- Charter Of Fundamental Rights Of The European Union
https://www.europarl.europa.eu/charter/pdf/text_en.pdf
- European Convention on Human Rights
https://www.echr.coe.int/documents/convention_eng.pdf
- An example of Inclusive Practices in Research Environment: Video
<https://youtu.be/rS4ci68dGc4>
- Harvard Business Review: How Diversity Can Drive Innovation
<https://hbr.org/2013/12/how-diversity-can-drive-innovation>
- The Royal Society: Research Culture: Embedding inclusive excellence
<https://royalsociety.org/topics-policy/publications/2018/research-culture-embedding-inclusive-excellence/>
- U.S. Equal Employment Opportunity Commission: Chart of Risk Factors for Harassment
<https://www.eeoc.gov/chart-risk-factors-harassment-and-responsive-strategies>

Unit3: GDPR General Framework

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
History and evolution of privacy and GDPR <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A brief evolution of the two concept will be provided to students through the sequence of laws and regulation in time 	Lectures: Francesco Di Tano - UniBO	10 min.
Feld of application and the subjects involved <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyzing the text of the Regulation and highlighting the different subjctcs and roles involved 	Lectures: Francesco Di Tano - UniBO	15 min.
GDPR principles <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students will be provided with a selection principles regulating the GDPR and their motives will be briefly analyzed in class 	Lectures: Francesco Di Tano - UniBO	20 min.
Categories of data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students will be shown the different categories of data, highlighting the particular categories and the types of protection required 	Lectures: Francesco Di Tano - UniBO	25 min.
Subjects of the treatment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students will be shown the different subjects validated in the data processing, their roles and responsibilities by referring to the text of the regulation 	Lectures: Francesco Di Tano - UniBO	15 min.
Informed consent <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Informed consent: referring to the text of the regulation will analyze the different types of consent, the contents and the legal basis and consent 	Lectures: Francesco Di Tano - UniBO	25 min.
“Dark patterns” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Introduction to the role of the European Data Protection Board in the identification of six macro-categories of dark patterns and their definitions 	Lectures + a brief online video (5 min.): Francesco Di Tano - UniBO	15 min.

<p>Practical exercise</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students will be invited to analyze an informed consent and appoint the mistakes and rewrite a correct one 	<p>Online and onsite in groups - possibility to give a delayed deadline to prepare the results</p>	<p>40 min.</p>

Teaching Materials

All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1v8ExhiSsglgnon7fihl0y4OadE-E6wW> (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

Unit 4: Public engagement and citizen science

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
<p>Analysis and discussion of the overall concepts of Public Engagement</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Definitions</i> • <i>What counts as public engagement in RIs</i> • <i>Typical methods of public engagement in different fields</i> • <i>Legal and other constraints in RIs affecting public engagement</i> • <i>Impact of public engagement, what and how to determine</i> 	Lecture and general discussion – theoretical part: Marco Peura - UH	45 min
<p>Case studies <i>Different concepts of Public Engagement in selected RIs will be reviewed and analysed. In addition to the pre-selected examples by the lecturer, attendees are requested to bring an example from their discipline or RI.</i> <i>For the pilot course, the case examples are selected from following:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Biobanking RIs (BBMRI, FinnGen project)</i> • <i>Biodiversity collection RI (case example FinBIF - Finnish Biodiversity information Centre)</i> • <i>CLARIAH and the Donate Speech initiative</i> • <i>EATRIS and the Patient Engagement Resource Centre</i> 	<p>Case studies analysis - presentation of different approaches to Public Engagement in RIs</p> <p>Discussion in small groups (breakout rooms when remote)</p> <p>Synthesis of the small groups' discussions with the whole group of attendees</p>	45 min
<p>Analysis and discussion of the overall concepts of citizen science</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>History and definitions</i> • <i>What is citizen science in different domains (esp. Life Sciences, Natural Sciences / STEM, SSH)</i> • <i>Citizen science and RIs, an overview</i> • <i>Legal and other constraints in RIs affecting citizen science</i> • <i>Access policies and overall accessibility: What enables / hinders citizen science in RIs?</i> 	Lecture and general discussion – theoretical part: Marco Peura - UH	45 min
<p>Case studies <i>Different approaches to Citizen Science in selected RIs will be reviewed and analysed. In addition to the pre-</i></p>		45 min

<p><i>selected examples by the lecturer, attendees are requested to bring an example from their discipline or RI.</i></p> <p><i>For the pilot course, the case examples are selected from following:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>BBMRI, FinnGen project</i> ● <i>FinBIF</i> ● <i>CLARIAH and the Donate Speech initiative</i> ● <i>ICOS RI</i> 	<p>Case studies analysis - presentation of different approaches to Citizen Science in RIs</p> <p>Discussion in small groups (breakout rooms when remote)</p> <p>Synthesis of small groups' discussions with the whole group of attendees</p>	
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Teaching Materials

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1nfWLJ30ihPFIKgrvX1yUmpAeFbOQmeeo/edit>

All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website

<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1v8ExhiSsglgnon7fihl0y4OadE-E6wW> (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

Innovation, entrepreneurship and engagement with industry

LEVEL EQF6 EQF7 EQF8

ECTS	2
LA Aims	Addressing questions like what an invention is and understanding how to exploit and valorise entrepreneurship to innovate and increase the impact on the RI or CF on society. Furthermore, the pathways and the elements to constitute successful and sustainable relationships between industry and the facilities will be elucidated, understanding how to overcome the major barriers leveraging on the added value for a successful engagement
Learning Goals	<p>Upon completion of this LA students will have demonstrated a basic knowledge of what innovation represents in the research infrastructure (RI) and a core facility (CF) lifecycle. In particular, they are expected to have learnt:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the definition of innovation from CF & RI perspectives; (b) the different ways for RIs and CF to engage with industry; (c) how to promote knowledge exchange and technology transfer and creating value; (d) how to transfer the potential value of an invention into a working facility; (e) the interplay (and connected challenges) between invention and entrepreneurship, that is, how to transform an invention into a useful product for society; (f) how to exploit the role of RIs and CF as “innovation hubs” (“demo-sites”, “test sites”, “application scouts”) (g) an understand of the Decision Making process (h) the main strategies to stimulate and sustain innovation (i) the main barriers to industry/RI-CF engagement
Specific Learning Outcomes (Los)	<p>After completing the course, the student is expected to be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Contextualise</i> the role of RI and CF in the overall contribution to Innovation • <i>Describe</i> different industry stakeholders based on characteristics including: sector, main activity, company size, or service needs to define a tailored engagement strategy and define an adopted define a proper engagement strategy • <i>Describe</i> the importance of industry engagement for public stakeholders and the main barriers to such engagement • <i>Explain</i> the main drivers, motivation, constraints and cultural differences in organizations and how they influence collaboration. • <i>Explain</i> what it takes to commit oneself and take on a role as an innovator.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Describe</i> how to protect your ideas (intellectual property, patent strategy, licensing, contracts, patent search), • <i>Describe</i> how to present your ideas, as well as give and receive feedback ("Elevator pitch". The last day of the course is organized as a "value creation forum") • <i>Describe</i> how to communicate an invention to different stakeholders in society and write a popular science text • <i>Explain</i> how to present scientific matters in a way likely to interest the private sector • <i>Describe</i> potential actions for an industry engagement strategy • <i>Describe</i> the diversity of needs and potentials when approaching the private sector • <i>Distinguish</i> between activities to be carried out by a RI/CF and others that can be supported externally • <i>Explain</i> how to negotiate boundaries in industry / academia
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Main characteristics of the LA

Format	Synchronous ONLINE course
Pedagogical methods/tools:	The course will combine theoretical aspects, showcases and testimonials from invited speakers, and practical sessions that take into consideration and draw inspiration from the diverse backgrounds of the participants. Basic concepts will be first introduced in traditional lectures, after which the participants get to demonstrate their understanding of the subject through showcases, exercises and teamwork assignments. Entrepreneurial journeys: every day of the course ends with invite entrepreneurs who talk about their experiences and reflect on the topic of the day
Assessment methods:	The examination of the course will be a written report from each student, and an individual oral examination. In addition, to pass the course the student must attend a minimum of 80% of the lectures.
Evaluation:	Participation in and use of the practical exercises during the course.
Bibliography/teaching materials:	Online course: Reference books, publications, presentations, web material, offline video recordings, show case studies and testimonials (academy, industry)
LA Leader	UGOT
LA Participants	UNIMIB, UniTN, University of Sussex Business School

Course description

The course does not require any specific knowledge background. The teaching consisting in lectures and group practicals with case study.

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
<p>From Creativity to Entrepreneurship – Innovation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Innovation management: Understand the definition of innovation in general and from CF & RI perspective types of innovation. Exploit effectively processes and tools for stimulating innovation and value creation. Master the main strategies to stimulate and sustain innovation.</i> • <i>Innovation Ecosystems from the RI and CF perspective: understand the actors of the RI/CF innovation ecosystems and their role. Transfer the potential value of an invention into a working facility. Contextualize the role of RI and CF in the overall contribution to Innovation. Understand External versus Internal Innovation</i> • <i>Valorisation of the infrastructures: Intellectual property and patents: Understand intellectual property and patents. Lear how to promote knowledge exchange and technology transfer and creating value. How to build a strategy for IP valorization. Describe and discuss the fundamentals of intellectual property rights and legislation, value and comment its importance for companies in different development stages, particularly in companies active within biotech or natural resource management.</i> • <i>CF and RI as Innovators Hubs: Understand the potential benefits and challenges of constant innovation for CF and RI.</i> • <i>Show cases and Testimonial from academic and industrial speakers: Innovation in CF and RI as: service provision; methodology/technology transfer; new technology development</i> 	<p>Lectures + testimonial + Show case study analysis + discussion</p> <p>Teachers: David Eggleton, Fabio Ledda and Julia Fernandez-Rodriguez</p>	<p>4 h</p>
<p>From Creativity to Entrepreneurship - Entrepreneurial venture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>The Startup Leadership Context: Introduction to Entrepreneurial Leadership: Understanding the basic concepts of Entrepreneurship. What is an</i> 	<p>Lectures + testimonial + Show case study analysis + discussion</p>	<p>4 h</p>

<p><i>entrepreneur? Understand the Decision-Making process. Identify and evaluate new business ideas: the role of investors. The Startup Leadership Context: Introduction to Entrepreneurial Leadership. the entrepreneurial process of wealth creation.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Creating, investigating and evaluating business ideas and opportunities: business planning for the entrepreneurial venture: Understand the fundamentals of business modelling. Understand the interplay between invention and entrepreneurship, that is, how to transform an invention into a useful product for society. Formulate a business strategy for the new venture that can be communicated to external stakeholders. Creating and sustaining competitive advantage in the entrepreneurial venture</i> • <i>Show cases and Testimonial from academic and industrial speakers: Entrepreneurship in CF and RI; Understanding strategic rationale and processes for commercial product development</i> 	<p>Teachers: David Eggleton, Fabio Ledda and Julia Fernandez-Rodriguez</p>	
<p>Engagement with industry</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>What motivates industry-facility working relationships (service vs collaboration/method development)?'</i> • <i>'How can we better align our interests for a successful relationship?'</i> • <i>Funding opportunities for industrial-academic collaboration projects.</i> • <i>The role of RI and CF in the overall contribution to Innovation</i> • <i>The role of RIs and CF as "innovation hubs" ("demo-sites", "test sites", "application scouts")</i> • <i>The different ways for RIs and CF to engage with industry.</i> • <i>The importance of the industry engagement for public stakeholders</i> • <i>How to segment industries to define a proper engagement strategy</i> • <i>Main barriers to industry/RI-CF engagement</i> • <i>The strategic role of the interaction with industry for the socio-economic impact of a RI and CF</i> 	<p>Lectures + testimonial + Show case study analysis + discussion</p> <p>Teachers: Ennio Capria, Ed Mitchell and Julia Fernandez-Rodriguez</p>	<p>4 h</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case studies/ Testimonial/ Exercises 		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hands-on exercises • Presenting the oral exam 	Student showcase	2 h

Teaching Materials

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1oBrAaTjtPgSTA6W1FEkXgVMTCAg_CWwl/edit#heading=h.gjdgxs

All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website

https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1gpvs3E4T0kZDa9IzMXezPbFb_-qVRBsq (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

1. Saskia Lippens, Christophe D'Enfert, Lilla Farkas, Anna Kehres, Bernhard Korn, Mònica Morales, Rainer Pepperkok, Lavanya Premvardhan, Ralph Schlapbach, Andreas Tiran, Doris Meder, & Geert Van Minnebruggen (2019). *One step ahead- Innovation in core facilities*. EMBO reports 20: e48017.
2. Chesbrough H (2003). *Open innovation: the new imperative for creating and profiting from technology*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business School Press
3. Christensen CM, Raynor M, McDonald R (2015). *What is disruptive innovation?* Harv Bus Rev 93: 44 – 53
4. Osterwalder, A., & Pigneur, Y. (2010). *Business model generation: a handbook for visionaries, game changers, and challengers*. Wiley.com
5. *Guides to IPR management - European IP Helpdesk library*: <http://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/IP-Guides>
6. Scarrà D, Piccaluga A. *The impact of technology transfer and knowledge spillover from Big Science: a literature review*. Technovation. 2022; 116:102165. doi:[10.1016/j.technovation.2020.102165](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2020.102165)
7. Tidd J, Bessant JR. *Managing Innovation: Integrating Technological, Market and Organizational Change*. John Wiley & Sons; 2020.
8. Clo S, Florio M. *Science, innovation, and public services: editorial introduction*. Journal of Economic Policy Reform. 2020;23(1):1-15. doi:[10.1080/17487870.2019.1649149](https://doi.org/10.1080/17487870.2019.1649149)
9. Magazinik A, Bedolla JS, Lasheras NC, Makinen S. *Societal impact as Cost-Benefit Analysis: Comparative analysis of two research infrastructures*. In: 2019 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology and Innovation (ICE/ITMC). ; 2019. doi:[10.1109/ICE.2019.8792600](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICE.2019.8792600)
10. Dal Molin M, Previtali E. *Basic research public procurement: the impact on supplier companies*. Journal of Public Procurement. 2019;19(3):224-251. doi:[10.1108/JOPP-07-2018-0027](https://doi.org/10.1108/JOPP-07-2018-0027)
11. Autio E, Hameri A, Vuola O. *A framework of industrial knowledge spillovers in big-science centers*. RESEARCH POLICY. 2004;33(1):107-126. doi:[10.1016/S0048-7333\(03\)00105-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(03)00105-7)
12. Salter AJ, Martin BR. *The economic benefits of publicly funded basic research: a critical review*. Research Policy. 2001;30(3):509-532. doi:[Doi 10.1016/S0048-7333\(00\)00091-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0048-7333(00)00091-3)
13. Stokes DE. *Pasteur's Quadrant: Basic Science and Technological Innovation*. Brookings Institution Press; 1997.
14. Autio E, Hameri A, Nordberg M. *A framework of motivations for industry big science collaboration: A case study*. JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY MANAGEMENT. 1996;13(3-4):301-314. doi:[10.1016/S0923-4748\(96\)01011-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0923-4748(96)01011-9)
15. Eggleton D. *Evaluating the impact of big science/research infrastructures*. In: Panagiotis, C., Theodore A., Harry C., Gunther, Dissertori, Juliette F., Jason L. (Eds.) *Big Science in the 21st Century: Economic and Societal Impacts*. Institute of Physics Publishing; 2022.

Communicating Research in the Social Media Era: Concepts and Practical Tools

LEVEL EQF6 EQF7 EQF8

ECTS	2
LA Aims	<p>The course aims at presenting the general area of scientific communication, setting the activity into a historical perspective, and into the current wider perspective connecting research funding and implied dissemination activities. The course also aims at presenting a selection of practical tools supporting the setup, organisation, and management of web sites for scientific communication.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With respect to ERC sectors the course has some relevance to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PE6_10 - Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion • SH3_12 - Communication and information, networks, media • SH6_15 - History of science, medicine and technologies
Learning Goals	<p>Upon completion of this LA students will have demonstrated a general understanding of aims and issues related to scientific communication, as well as practical ability to configure and organize web-based systems supporting scientific communication. Students will also learn the basics of web-based content management systems (CMS).</p>
Selected Learning Outcomes (LOs):	<p>After completing the course, the student is expected to be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • define at least two key moments of history of scientific communication and past approaches; • describe the fundamentals of current scientific communication trends; • explain the fundamental relationships between scientific communication and current practice in research funding; • adopt a popular CMS (Wordpress) to structure a scientific communication website.

Main characteristics of the LA

Format	Blended (Units 1 to 4 can be held online, asynchronously; units 5 and 6 are to be held in presence)
Pedagogical methods/tools:	Lectures and group practical activities

Assessment methods:	Embedded assessments (students will produce in Unit 5 a small project that will be publicly discussed and evaluated in Unit 6 with feedback from the instructor)
Evaluation:	Students need to prepare: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A specific digital content (a presentation, a blog post, a short video) to communicate a research result to a specific audience within the popular stage level; • The structure, a draft of the planned style, and some initial contents of a website based on Wordpress / other CMS of choice presenting a specific research project to an audience mostly set in the popular stage level; • The plan of a research dissemination event / initiative, considering a specific audience mostly set in the popular stage level.
LA Leader	UNIMIB Giuseppe Vizzari
LA Participants	-

Course Description

Three Days, 16h intensive course. The course aims at introducing concepts and practical tools supporting scientific communication through web channels. We expect to run 6 teaching units consisting in lectures (aimed at providing both conceptual and practical knowledge) and group practical activities, involving groups of students in small projects related to their ongoing research / projects:

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
Scientific communication: history and general framework	Lecture and discussion: Giuseppe Vizzari - UNIMIB	3 h
Content Management Systems for modern web sites	Lecture and discussion: Giuseppe Vizzari - UNIMIB	3 h
Scientific communication: current trends, discussion	Lecture and discussion: Giuseppe Vizzari - UNIMIB	3 h
Wordpress for running a scientific communication website	Lecture and discussion: Giuseppe Vizzari - UNIMIB	3 h
Group practical activities		2 h
Group work discussion		2 h

Teaching Materials

Short textbook (slides), videos, and examples of practical cases for group activities

All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website

<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1tQZrgZxYWtEy5FImkMP-3hBVM08J9FwJ> (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

Communicating Research – Introduction to Science to Science and Science to Public Communication

LEVEL EQF6 EQF7 EQF8

ECTS	2
LA Aims	<p>The course aims to provide students with a basic understanding of how to communicate their research to different target groups, why this is necessary for good scientific practice and what can be done to achieve this.</p> <p>The course will introduce students to different forms of text suited for different types of science communication and provide them with an idea on what to take into account when writing materials for different purposes. Furthermore, it will introduce students to different tools and resources that are available to host their content in a persistent way and what different offerings like dedicated homepages, different content repositories and editable hubs for their research exist and provide them with the knowledge to select the correct tools for their demands.</p>
Learning Goals	<p>Upon completion of this LA students will have demonstrated a basic knowledge of how to communicate their research. In particular, they are expected to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) understand the relationship between science and the public sphere (the purpose of science communication) (b) learn the fundamentals of scientific communication when addressing the scientific community (e.g. other researchers, research infrastructures) (c) learn the fundamentals of scientific communication when addressing the research adjunct organisations (e.g. funders, research support) (d) learn the fundamentals of scientific communication when addressing the public / public sphere (e.g. policy makers, journalists) (e) learn about the basic tools to support scientific communication (e.g. What is Zenodo for? What is GITHUB for? What is a data repository for? What is social media for? What is my institutional homepage for? Who can those be linked? What purpose does press coverage have?) (f) understand why it is necessary address different target groups concerning science communication differently (public, researchers, research-adjunct organisation)

Selected Learning Outcomes	<p>Upon completion of this LA students will be able to</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • differentiate between different forms of Science Communication • structure and arrange their materials to match the expectations of their identified target groups. • identify what type of information will be needed for which target group and structure their materials accordingly. • organize a workflow to publish and disseminate their materials in the relevant channels. • select a suitable way to publish their materials within the European Open Science Framework and their institutional surroundings.
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Main characteristics of the LA

Format	In-person / synchronous
Pedagogical methods/tools:	Lectures, Presentations and group practical activities
Assessment methods:	Embedded assessments (students will produce materials in the afternoon sessions on each day that will be the foundation of assessing their participation, additionally two pieces of communication materials will be handed in for additional evaluation)
Evaluation:	<p>Students need to prepare:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 short Presentations (during the intensive course) • 2 short communication pieces (max 4000 words) and a description on how they will be used
LA Leader	JKU - Dimitri Prandner
LA Participants	-

Course Description

Each day will be split into a morning session, consisting in lectures and discussions. Those will provide conceptual knowledge and allow to discuss the potential for application in a particular field of research. After a noon break it will be followed by practical group activities in the afternoon. Those will guide the students towards creating suitable content under the supervision of the lecturer.

Ideally the students join the course when they have already decided on a research project for the PhD thesis.

A month after the workshop the participants have to hand in a two pieces of communication materials dealing with their project including a short sketch how the materials can be used to meet the demands of a specific target group. These pieces and the strategy presented will be evaluated.

With respect to ERC sectors the course has some relevance to:

- PE6_10 - Web and information systems, data management systems, information retrieval and digital libraries, data fusion
- SH3_12 - Communication and information, networks, media
- SH6_15 - History of science, medicine and technologies

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
Communicating Science <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Expectations, Target groups and why researchers should care?</i> 	Lecture and discussion: Dimitri Prandner - JKU	3 h
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Identifying the target groups of specific projects and what they may need to know? This includes research on the target groups, the act of defining them etc</i> 	Tutorial / Groupwork	3 h
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Each group provides insight into their concept and it is discussed shortly</i> 	Student's Presentation	1 h
How to write and how to present research for different target groups: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Best practices, pitfalls and considerations</i> 	Lecture and discussion: Dimitri Prandner - JKU	3 h
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Each group outlines how it would deal with the demands found in different target groups and do research on how they would meet those demands for their research topic.</i> 	Tutorial / Groupwork	2 h
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Each group presents their findings and the outcomes will be discussed in a supportive manner</i> 	Student's Presentation	2 h
Introduction to different tools and different methods of science communication. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Prototypical workflow for science communication will be discussed</i> 	Lecture and discussion: Dimitri Prandner - JKU	3 h
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Each group searches for suitable tools to prepare materials to communicate their research topic</i> 	Tutorial / Groupwork	2 h

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Each group presents their findings and the outcomes will be discussed in a supportive manner</i> 	<p>Student's Presentation</p>	<p>2 h</p>
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Teaching materials

Short textbook (slides), three journal articles on science communication (tbd.), several examples of practical cases for group activities. All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1O_f2wEYapDrU0nM69FtY1T4umpFU7sxi (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

RESEARCH DATA MANAGEMENT

LEVEL EQF6 EQF7 EQF8

ECTS	2
LA Aims	The aim of this course is to provide students with the skills needed to manage the research data of a research project, taking into account the data policy of an institution.
Learning Goals	Upon completion of this LA students are expected to: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. Learn the fundamentals of the Data Lifecycle II. Understand the FAIR principles III. Acquire the skills to write a Data Management Plan. At institutional and European level. IV. Identify sensitive data in your datasets and manage it.
Selected Learning Outcomes	Upon the completion of this LA, students will be able: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● to manage the research data generated in projects, ● to write a Data Management Plan and ● to understand the data policy defined by an institution.

Main characteristics of the LA

Format	The format of the course will be blended. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Theoretical lessons will be resources published for the community. ● Use cases will be lectures given by invited speakers by online. ● The practical exercises will be a face to face activity.
Pedagogical methods/tools:	Presentations, lectures and group exercises
Assessment methods:	Each theoretical lesson will have a short questionnaire to assess the knowledge acquired by the student. The practical exercises will be evaluated based on the quality of the work presented and in the oral presentation. Also, the participation of the student (making questions) during the other students' presentations will be taken into account.
Evaluation:	The student will be evaluated based on quantitative and qualitative metrics. The practical exercises will be evaluated based on public rubrics.
LA Leader	UPM
LA Participants	UNIBO

Course Description

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time
Introduction to Research Data Management: Data Life Cycle.		1 hour
<i>Students learn the role of data in the research process and in research projects.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	10 min
<i>Understand the different research artifacts (datasets, software, publications, etc.) involved in a research.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	15 min
<i>Comprehend the evolution of the data in a research project, from raw data to processed data.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	25 min
<i>Discussion with students about the data managed in their thesis.</i>	Case discussion	10 min
Introduction to FAIR principles.		1 hour
<i>Reason why FAIR data is important and its role in Europe.</i>	Lectures: Silvio Peroni UniBO	10 min
<i>Understand each principle of the FAIR data. We will analyze each principle and its meaning.</i>	Lectures: Silvio Peroni UniBO	30 min
<i>Know the reference paper about FAIR data. Students will have to read the paper before the session.</i>	Case discussion	10 min
<i>Discussion with students about how they can apply FAIR principles in their thesis and the value to do it.</i>	Case discussion	10 min
Ethical and legal considerations. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Students will understand the ethical and legal aspects of the data and how to manage them. This will include the different licences used for data.</i> ● <i>Students will learn how to handle sensitive data.</i> 		2 hours
<i>Understand what is a license and why is important. Students will learn the different parts of a license.</i>	Lectures: Victor Rodriguez - UPM	10 min

Identify the main licenses used in researching both open and private.	Lectures: Victor Rodriguez - UPM	20 min
Apply a license to your work. Students will analyze their data and will select a license to apply them.	Lecture, case discussion: Victor Rodriguez - UPM	20 min
Identify any kind of sensitive data present in your research. Different representative cases will be exposed. For example: personal data, protected species, etc.	Lectures: Victor Rodriguez - UPM	30 min
Understand the main points in the GDPR and learn how to manage them	Lectures: Victor Rodriguez - UPM	20 min
Apply the GDPR to the data generated in their research	Case discussion	20 min
Practical exercise: Amnesia. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In this unit, students will learn how to use the tool Amnesia, from OpenAire, to anonymize sensitive data. 		2 hours
Acquire the skills to use tools like AMNESIA. We will use a video created by the OpenAIRE team.	Video (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0lo6c1MPOY)	60 min
Apply pseudonymization techniques to their data using the tool AMNESIA.	Case discussion	60 min
Data publication & Metadata standards. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students will learn how to share and publish their data, following the most popular standards. 		1 hour
Understand what is metadata	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	5 min
Understand what is a schema and the most popular (DCAT, Dublin Core, etc.)	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	55 min
Practical exercise: Zenodo <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In this unit, students will learn how to share and publish their data in Zenodo, a general-purpose repository. 		2 hours

<p><i>Learn how to use a repository as Zenodo to publish your research. We will use a video created by the OpenAIRE team.</i></p>	<p>Video (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yj2r8RaylX8)</p>	60 min
<p><i>Identify repositories where you can publish your data and how to do it (metadata that should be completed to be FAIR).</i></p>	Case discussion	60 min
<p>Introduction to a Data Management Plan.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>In this lesson, the different sections of a DMP will be described.</i> 		1 hour
<p><i>Understand the different sections of a DMP. We will focus on the template used for European projects (Horizon).</i></p>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	60 min
<p>Practical exercise: Argos.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Students will see a real implementation of a Data Management Plan. The tool Argos (OpenAIRE) will be used during the exercise.</i> 		2 hours
<p><i>Learn how to use the tool Argos to create DMPs. We will use a video created by the OpenAIRE team.</i></p>	<p>Video (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xOdcmankdj4)</p>	60 min
<p><i>Students will know representative use cases of DMPs (different domains). These examples will help them to create a DMP for their data.</i></p>	Lecture, case discussion: Esteban González - UPM	60 min
<p>Practical exercise.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Students will be divided in groups and they will have to create a Data Management Plan. After this, students will have to present their work to the other students.</i> 	(2 hours of team work + 2 hours presentations depending on the number of groups)	4 hours
<p><i>Learn how to write a DMP. The students will be grouped in teams and they will work in a real case.</i></p>	Practical exercise	120 min
<p><i>Students will present their DMP, where the other students will have to identify potential problems.</i></p>	Case discussion	120 min

Teaching materials

Presentations + notes for theoretical lessons

Teamwork material for practical exercises

Questionnaires

All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website

<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1kn8jaQbqbw5sE1W3IB6JE9niQAVinPoH> (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/ Sitography/ Video

- Bahlai, C., Bartlett, L., Burgio, K., Fournier, A., Keiser, C., Poisot, T., & Whitney, K. (2019). Open Science Isn't Always Open to All Scientists. *American Scientist*, 107(2), 78. <https://doi.org/10.1511/2019.107.2.78>
- Hendricks, G., Tkaczyk, D., Lin, J., & Feeney, P. (2020). Crossref: The sustainable source of community-owned scholarly metadata. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 1(1), 414–427. https://doi.org/10.1162/qss_a_00022
- Avanço, K., Balula, A., Błaszczczyńska, M., Buchner, A., Caliman, L., Clivaz, C., Costa, C., Franczak, M., Gatti, R., Giglia, E., Gingold, A., Jarmelo, S., Padez, M. J., Leão, D., Maryl, M., Melinščak Zlodi, I., Mojsak, K., Morka, A., Mosterd, T., ... Wieneke, L. (2021). Future of Scholarly Communication—Forging an inclusive and innovative research infrastructure for scholarly communication in Social Sciences and Humanities (p. 46). Digital Humanities Centre at the Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5017705>
- Belhajjame, K., B'Far, R., Cheney, J., Coppens, S., Cresswell, S., Gil, Y., Groth, P., Klyne, G., Lebo, T., McCusker, J., Miles, S., Myers, J., Sahoo, S., & Tilmes, C. (2013). PROV-DM: The PROV Data Model (L. Moreau & P. Missier, Eds.). World Wide Web Consortium. <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-dm/>
- Chue Hong, N. P., Katz, D. S., Barker, M., Lamprecht, A.-L., Martinez, C., Psomopoulos, F. E., Harrow, J., Castro, L. J., Gruenpeter, M., Martinez, P. A., & Honeyman, T. (2022). FAIR Principles for Research Software (FAIR4RS Principles) [Recommendations with RDA Endorsement in Process]. Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00068>
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), no. L119, Official Journal of the European Union (2016). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>
- GO FAIR. (2018). FAIR Principles. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
- Gualandi, B. (2022). What do we mean by 'data' in the arts and humanities? [Master thesis, University of Bologna]. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6385132>
- Haak, L. L., Fenner, M., Paglione, L., Pentz, E., & Ratner, H. (2012). ORCID: A system to uniquely identify researchers. *Learned Publishing*, 25(4), 259–264. <https://doi.org/10.1087/20120404>
- Kramer, B., & Bosman, J. (2015, June 18). The good, the efficient and the open—Changing research workflows and the need to move from Open Access to Open Science. CERN Workshop on Innovations in Scholarly Communication (OAI9), University of Geneva, Geneva, Switzerland. <https://www.slideshare.net/bmkramer/the-good-the-efficient-and-the-open-oai9>
- Landi, A., Thompson, M., Giannuzzi, V., Bonifazi, F., Labastida, I., da Silva Santos, L. O. B., & Roos, M. (2020). The “A” of FAIR – As Open as Possible, as Closed as Necessary. *Data Intelligence*, 2(1–2), 47–55. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00027
- Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I., Downs, R. R., Edmunds, R., Giaretta, D., De Giusti, M., L'Hours, H., Hugo, W., Jenkyns, R., Khodiyar, V., Martone, M. E., Mokrane, M., Navale, V., Petters, J., Sierman, B., Sokolova, D. V., Stockhouse, M., & Westbrook, J. (2020). The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Scientific Data*, 7(1), 144. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>
- Michener, W. K. (2015). Ten Simple Rules for Creating a Good Data Management Plan. *PLOS Computational Biology*, 11(10), e1004525. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1004525>
- Open Knowledge Foundation. (2015). Open Definition 2.1. <https://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/>
- Piwowar, H., Priem, J., Larivière, V., Alperin, J. P., Matthias, L., Norlander, B., Farley, A., West, J., & Haustein, S. (2017). Data From: The State Of Oa: A Large-Scale Analysis Of The Prevalence And Impact Of Open Access Articles [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.837901>
- Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., ... Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- Wolfe, M. (2017, August 9). CC0 and Data Citation. <https://www.library.ucdavis.edu/news/cc0-and-data-citation/>

RESEARCH DATA POLICY

LEVEL EQF6 EQF7 EQF8

ECTS	2
LA Aims	The aim of this course is to provide students with the skills needed to define and to implement the data policies of an institution.
Learning Goals	Upon the completion of this LA, students will be able to understand and to define the data policy of an institution.
Selected Learning Outcomes	<p>Upon the completion of this LA, students will be able:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● to define and implement a data policy for an institution, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ FAIR principles ▪ Licences ▪ Infrastructure needed (repositories & human resources) ▪ Data Management Plan ▪ Personal & Sensitive data

Main characteristics of the LA

Format	<p>The format of the course will be blended.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Theoretical lessons will be resources published for the community. ● Use cases will be lectures given by invited speakers by online. ● The practical exercises will be a face-to-face activity.
Pedagogical methods/tools:	Presentations, lectures and group exercises
Assessment methods:	<p>Each theoretical lesson will have a short questionnaire to assess the knowledge acquired by the student.</p> <p>The practical exercises (DMP and data policy) will be evaluated based on the quality of the work and the oral presentation. Also, the student participation (making questions) during the other students' presentations will be taken into account.</p>
Evaluation:	<p>The student will be evaluated based on quantitative and qualitative metrics.</p> <p>The practical exercises will be evaluated based on public rubrics.</p>
LA Leader	UPM
LA Participants	UNIBO

Course Description

Learning Goal	Learning model	Time (minutes)
Introduction to Research Data Management: Data Life Cycle. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brief introduction to research data life cycle, which stages must be defined in the data policy 		1 hour
<i>The role of data in the research process and in research projects.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	10 min
<i>Understand the different research artifacts (datasets, software, publications, etc.) involved in a research.</i>	1 Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	15 min
<i>Comprehend the evolution of the data in a research project, from raw data to processed data.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	25 min
<i>Discussion with students about the data managed in their thesis.</i>	Case discussion	10 min
Open & Private data. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The students will learn the difference between the two models, and how to implement them in a research environment. We will focus on FAIR principles and the main licences used for both sharing policies. 		1 hour
<i>Understand each principle of the FAIR data.</i>	Lectures: Victor Rodriguez - UPM	20 min
<i>Identify the main licenses used in researching both open and private.</i>	Lectures: Victor Rodriguez - UPM	20 min
<i>Understand the main points in the GDPR and learn how to manage them</i>	Lectures: Victor Rodriguez - UPM	20 min
Main data infrastructures elements in an organisation. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The student will learn what is a data repository, a data management plan tool, a data storage service, etc. 		1 hour

<i>Understand what is a data repository and the different policies applied to publish on it. We analyze concepts like metadata schemas and persistent identifiers.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	30 min
<i>Understand what is a data management plan and the tools that can be used to create it</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	30 min
Use case: Institutional and European data infrastructures. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>In this unit, we present a representative collection of data infrastructures based on partners' institutions infrastructures and European as EOSC services.</i> 		2 hours
<i>Analyze the data infrastructures of students' institutions</i>	Case discussion	50 min
<i>Identify EOSC data tools such as Zenodo, Argos, B2Share, Amnesia, B2Handle, AMNESIA, etc .</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	50 min
<i>Learn how EOSC tools can be adopted in the students' institutions</i>	Case discussion	20 min
Introduction to Data Governance. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Students will learn the main aspects of an institutional data policy, which includes how the data is gathered, stored, processed, etc.</i> 		1 hour
<i>Learn the different sections of a data policy. It includes, where data can be published, how to manage the GDPR, where and how private data can be stored, etc.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	60 min
Roles and Responsibilities of a data stewardship organisation. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>This unit will show how to create a data stewardship and how to integrate it in the institution's structure. Also, we analyse the different roles of a data steward.</i> 		1 hour

<i>Learn how data managers are structured in different organizations.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	20 min
<i>Learn the functions of data stewardship.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	20 min
<i>Learn how to acquire the skills to be a data stewardship.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	20 min
Data governance tools. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>In this unit, students will learn the use of some tools to communicate the data policies to the staff. This includes websites, communication plans, training courses, networking and roadmaps.</i> 		2 hours
<i>Understand the different tools the use of some tools to communicate the data policies to the staff.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	15 min
<i>Learn how to structure a website to show the data policies to researchers.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	15 min
<i>Define a communication plan to assure that researchers know the data policy.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	15 min
<i>Learn how to prepare training courses for researchers</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	15 min
<i>Define a roadmap to apply data policies in a research infrastructure</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	60 min
Data policies use cases. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>In this unit, we will analyse the different data policies defined in several institutions.</i> 		2 hours
<i>Know the data policies landscape in europe. We will focus on universities and research facilities.</i>	Lectures: Esteban González - UPM	60 min
<i>Comprehend the data policies implemented in students' institutions</i>	Case discussion	60 min
Practical exercise. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Students will be divided in groups and they will have to elaborate a data policy for a research institution. They will present the work to the other students</i> 	(2 hours of team work + 2 hours presentations depending on the number of the group)	4 hours

<i>Learn how to write a data policy document. The students will be grouped in groups and they will work in a real case</i>	Practical exercise	120 min
<i>Students will present their data policies, where the other students will have to identify potential problems.</i>	Case discussion	120 min

Teaching Materials

All the PowerPoint material used for the lecture will be made available to the students at the dedicated website <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1kn8jaQbqbw5sE1W3IB6JE9niQAVinPoH> (the folder will be populated during the piloting of the courses)

Bibliography/Sitography/Videos

- Kramer, B., & Bosman, J. (2015, June 18). The good, the efficient and the open—Changing research workflows and the need to move from Open Access to Open Science. CERN Workshop on Innovations in Scholarly Communication (OAI9), University of Geneva, Geneva, Switzerland. <https://www.slideshare.net/bmkramer/the-good-the-efficient-and-the-open-oai9>
- Meng, X.-L. (2020). Reproducibility, Replicability, and Reliability. *Harvard Data Science Review*, 2(4). <https://doi.org/10.1162/99608f92.dbfce7f9>
- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), no. L119, Official Journal of the European Union (2016). <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>
- GO FAIR. (2018). FAIR Principles. <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
- Perneger, T. V. (2004). Writing a research article: Advice to beginners. *International Journal for Quality in Health Care*, 16(3), 191–192. <https://doi.org/10.1093/intqhc/mzh053>
- Lamprecht, A.-L., Garcia, L., Kuzak, M., Martinez, C., Arcila, R., Martin Del Pico, E., Dominguez Del Angel, V., van de Sandt, S., Ison, J., Martinez, P. A., McQuilton, P., Valencia, A., Harrow, J., Psomopoulos, F., Gelpi, J. Ll., Chue Hong, N., Goble, C., & Capella-Gutierrez, S. (2020). Towards FAIR principles for research software. *Data Science*, 3(1), 37–59. <https://doi.org/10.3233/DS-190026>
- Alexandrov, A. V., & Hennerici, M. G. (2013). How to Prepare and Deliver a Scientific Presentation. *Cerebrovascular Diseases*, 35(3), 202–208. <https://doi.org/10.1159/000346077>
- Allen, L., O’Connell, A., & Kiermer, V. (2019). How can we ensure visibility and diversity in research contributions? How the Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) is helping the shift from authorship to contributorship. *Learned Publishing*, 32(1), 71–74. <https://doi.org/10.1002/leap.1210>
- Aspesi, C., & Brand, A. (2020). In pursuit of open science, open access is not enough. *Science*, 368(6491), 574–577. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aba3763>
- Bilder, G., Lin, J., & Neylon, C. (2020). The Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure. *The Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure*. <https://doi.org/10.24343/C34W2H>
- Burgelman, J.-C. (2021). Politics and Open Science: How the European Open Science Cloud Became Reality (the Untold Story). *Data Intelligence*, 3(1), 5–19. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_a_00069
- Doumont, J. (2011). Creating Effective Presentation Slides. *Optics & Photonics News*, 22(3), 12–14. https://www.osa-opn.org/home/articles/volume_22/issue_3/departments/career_focus/creating_effective_presentation_slides/
- Ficarra, V., Fosci, M., Chiarelli, A., Kramer, B., & Proudman, V. (2020). Scoping the Open Science Infrastructure Landscape in Europe. *SPARC Europe*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4159838>

- Kramer, B., & Bosman, J. (2015, June 18). The good, the efficient and the open—Changing research workflows and the need to move from Open Access to Open Science. CERN Workshop on Innovations in Scholarly Communication (OAI9), University of Geneva, Geneva, Switzerland. <https://www.slideshare.net/bmkramer/the-good-the-efficient-and-the-open-oai9>
- Skinner, K., & Lippincott, S. (2020). Assessment Checklist (Commonplace). Knowledge Futures Group. <https://doi.org/10.21428/6ffd8432.5175bab1/00710d8a>
- Teal, T., Lowenberg, D., Smith, T., Gonzales, J. B., Nielsen, L. H., & Ioannidis, A. (2020, August 26). Sustainable, Open Source Alternatives Exist [Blog]. Dryad News and Views. <https://blog.datadryad.org/2020/08/26/sustainable-infrastructure-exists/>
- Teperek, M., & Dunning, A. (2020, August 18). Why figshare? Choosing a new technical infrastructure for 4TU.ResearchData [Blog]. Open Working. <https://openworking.wordpress.com/2020/08/18/why-figshare-choosing-a-new-technical-infrastructure-for-4tu-researchdata/>
- Aalto university (Research Data Management Videos). <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jZn1d2DZpro&list=PLa0sKMV88Js4La7rqVBxzW4NwRWygVdYj>